

Smart Blind Guidance Using Arduino

Zainab Faeq Jaafar, Batool Hussein Abed Naser,
Aya Mohammed Kadhim, Zahraa Ahmed Mohsin

Department of Medical Instruments Techniques Engineering, Al-Hussein University College, Iraq

Suggested Citation

Jaafar, Z.F., Naser, B.H.A.,
Kadhim, A.M., & Mohsin, Z.A.
(2024). Smart Blind Guidance
Using Arduino. *European Journal of
Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(4),
907-916.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(4\).74](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(4).74)

Abstract:

Vision is a beautiful gift to humans. This paper aims to develop an ultrasonic sensor based smart Guidance prototype as an electronic travel aid for blind people that can help them travel independently. The smart cap consists of ATmega microcontroller, Arduino board, three ultrasonic sensors, and a buzzer. Simulation of the system is provided for understanding the concept and to check its functioning. Proteus 8 simulation environment has been used for this purpose. Smart cap is a closed loop control system that continuously monitors the presence of any object around it and feedbacks the output to

input for comparison. Finally, a step by step process of hardware connections has been provided.

Keywords: *ultrasonic sensor, electronic travel aid, simulation environment, smart blind cap.*

Introduction

The technologies always try to make human life easier. The people who are visually Impaired they faces many difficulties during navigation. India is home to the largest number of visually impaired people in the world, about 40 million, which accounts for 20% of the world's blind population. Moreover, more than 90% of these people have little to no access to the necessary assistive technologies. Blindness can be occurring due to many reasons including disease, injury or other conditions that limit vision. In this paper, we design and implement a smart cap, which helps the blind and the visually impaired people to navigate freely by experiencing their surroundings. The objective of this research study is to design an assistive wearable cap for the blind or visually impaired persons. The solution present is an assistive wearable 'Smart Cap' that helps people with visual impairment interact and navigate their way to safety by wearing a cap fitted with a Ultrasonic Sensor.

The aim purpose of develop a cap for blind which will guide them from their source to destination. Smart cap is easy for who live alone. This solution is also support visually impaired people to navigate their way too safely and identify dangerous objects.

Objectives of the Project

The main purpose of this project is to design and implement a smart blind cap using ultra sound distance measurement sensors to calculate distance from the distance from the device. The signal comes from the receiver to the transmitter and increases the speed of the crystal clock. So the signal transmits the quick received. The first recipient receives signals from sensors and send signals in the microcontroller. The microcontroller controls the signal at a specific distance of 100 cm, 50 cm and other functionality of 30cm compress motor.

1. Precise and fix measurement of low range distance.

2. To measure a distance at any obstacle.
3. Design a simple circuit and find a suitable hardware for this project.

Scope of Work

When this project will work, if it an obstacle of 100 cm, 50 cm then give a sound. When it gets closer, the total will go near 60 cm double signals. If for some reason blind people do not listen to this world, then the vibration motor will vibrate, near the obstacle around 30 cm, Basic principle of Smart Blind Guidance, The electronic principle on which the smart cap

operates is very similar to the principle of sound-wave reflection. If you shout in the direction of a sound- reflecting object (like a rocky canyon or cave), you will hear an echo. If you know the speed of sound in air, you can then estimate the distance and general direction of the object. The time required for an echo to return can be roughly converted to distance if the speed of sound is known. Smart Blind Guidance uses electromagnetic energy pulses in much the same way, as shown in Figure 1. The radio-frequency energy is transmitted to and reflected from the reflecting object, a small portion of the reflected energy returns to smart cap.

Figure 1. Basic principle of Smart Blind Guidance

The aim of this project: The aim of this project work is to provide an assistive technology to help the visually impaired navigate their way out of any potentially disastrous situations as if other citizens would. The proposed system and its usage in disaster situations is an innovative, cost-effective solution specifically addressing the needs of visually impaired persons.

Components and Their Description

In this chapter, theoretical concept of the proposed system will be presented the designed system consists of two parts: Hardware parts and Software parts (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Two Parts: Hardware Parts and Software Parts

Hardware Parts

Arduino UNO R3

Arduino is an open-source computer hardware, open-source software and interactive objects that can microcontroller-based device building kit, sense, and control physical devices. Arduino designs and manufactures software. The project is focused on the design of the software, software and Microcontrollers. The board contains a combination of digital and analog Input / output (I / O) pins, which can connect to specific expansion boards communication interfaces for loading (termed shields). The plates have serial programs from personal computers, including Universal Serial Bus (USB). The Arduino project provides the built-in development Nano environment (IDE) for the programming of micro controlling systems to allow code writing and uploading to the board. It runs on Mac OS X, Java, which is based on open Linux and Windows.

The Arduino UNO board is shown in figure 3.

Figure 3. Arduino UNO

Table 1 Features of Arduino at a Glance

Microcontroller	ATmega328
Operating Voltage	5V
Input Voltage (recommended)	7-12V
Input Voltage (limits)	6-20V
Digital I/O Pins	14 (of which 6 provide PWM output)
Analog Input Pins	6
DC Current per I/O Pin	40 mA

DC Current for 3.3V Pin	50 mA
Flash Memory	32 KB (ATmega328) of which 0.5 KB used by bootloader
SRAM	2 KB (ATmega328)
EEPROM	1 KB (ATmega328)
Clock Speed	16 MHz

Ultrasonic Sensor-Hc-SRO4

Ultrasonic sensor is mainly used to determine the distance of the target object. Transmitter and receiver are two main parts of the sensor where former converts an electrical signal to ultrasonic waves while later converts that ultrasonic signals back to electrical signals. Its operating frequency is 4 MHz and its detection range is from 2cm to 150 cm.

In this project, we use three Ultrasonic Sensor.

Figure 4. Ultra-Sonic HC-SR04

Ultrasound is high-pitched sound waves with frequencies higher than the audible limit of human hearing.

Figure 5. Sound Waves

Human ears can hear sound waves that vibrate in the range from about 20 times a second (a deep rumbling noise) to about 20,000 times a second (a high-pitched whistling). However, ultrasound has a frequency of over 20,000 Hz and is therefore inaudible to humans.

Here are complete specifications:

Table 2. Complete Specifications to Ultrasonic HC-SR04

Operating Voltage	DC 5V
Operating Current	15mA
Operating Frequency	40KHz
Max Range	4m
Min Range	2cm
Ranging Accuracy	3mm
Measuring Angle	15 degree
Trigger Input Signal	10µS TTL pulse
Dimension	45 x 20 x 15mm

HC-SR04 Ultrasonic Sensor Pin out Look at its Pinout:

Figure 6. Ultrasonic Sensor Pin Out

VCC is the power supply for HC-SR04 Ultrasonic distance sensor which we connect the 5V pin on the Arduino. Trig (Trigger) pin is used to trigger the ultrasonic sound pulses, Echo pin produces a pulse when the reflected signal is received. The length of the pulse is proportional to the time it took for the transmitted signal to be detected. GND should be connected to the

ground of Arduino. It all starts, when a pulse of at least 10 µS (10 microseconds) in duration is applied to the Trigger pin. In response to that the sensor transmits a sonic burst of eight pulses at 40 KHz. This 8-pulse pattern makes the “ultrasonic signature” from the device unique, allowing the receiver to differentiate the transmitted pattern from the ambient ultrasonic noise.

The eight ultrasonic pulses travel through the air away from the transmitter. Meanwhile the Echo pin goes HIGH to start forming the beginning of the echo- back signal. If those pulses are not reflected back then the Echo signal will timeout after 38 mS (38 milliseconds) and return low. Thus a 38 mS pulse indicates no obstruction within the range of the sensor. If those pulses are reflected back the Echo pin goes low as soon as the signal is received. This produces a pulse whose width varies between 150 µS to 25 mS, depending upon the time it took for the signal to be received (Agrawal, & Gupta, 2018).

Figure 7. Working Principle of Ultrasonic Sensor

3-Rocker switch: A rocker switch is a type of switch that rocks back and forth, an action where one end is raised and the other is depressed, much like how a seesaw works when pressed, instead of tripping or staying depressed. One side of the switch is on and the other is off; these are usually marked with a "1" for on and "0" for off. Most common switches are rocker switches. In this project, we use three Rocker Switch.

Figure 8. Rocker Switch

4-piezo buzzer 12mm: A piezo buzzer. Piezo buzzers are like tiny little speakers, but unlike speakers they don't require an amplifier or other complex circuitry to drive them (consequently they aren't nearly as loud as a speaker and amplifier either!). When voltage is applied to the piezo it grows and shrinks in size, and by changing the voltage over time you can make the piezo change shape fast enough to create a pressure wave that your ears interpret as sound.

Figure 9. Piezo Buzzer

5-Jumper wires: Jumper wires are simply wires that have connector pins at each end, allowing them to be used to connect two points to each other without soldering. Jumper wires are typically used with breadboards and other prototyping tools in order to make it easy to change a circuit as needed, simple.

Figure 10. Jumper Wires

6-Breadboard: A thin plastic board used to hold electronic components that are wired together. Used to develop prototypes of electronic circuits, breadboards can be reused for future jobs. The breadboard contains spring clip contacts typically arranged in matrices with certain blocks of clips already wired together. The components and jump wires are plugged into the clips to create the circuit patterns.

Figure 11. Breadboard

7-Battery: The 3.7v lithium battery is a lithium battery with a nominal voltage of 3.7v and a full-charge voltage of 4.2v. Its capacity ranges from several hundred to several thousand mAh. It is generally used in various instruments and meters, testing instruments, medical instruments, POS machines, notebook computers, and other products.

Figure 12. Battery

8-hat: In order to install the components of the project on it.

Figure 13. Hat

The Smart Cap

The smart cap works on the lines of a radar system. Three ultrasonic sensors are reconnected in three different directions on the cap. An ultrasonic sensor has two parts, *trig* and *echo*. The *trig* releases wave and the wave reflects after striking an object and received by the *echo*. The *echo* behaves as a receiver. The three ultrasonic

sensors take the reading individually and send it to Arduino.

Arduino program calculates the distance of the object from the sensor. As per the program, if the distance is less than 1 m, then the buzzer sounds, and if it is more than 1 m the buzzer remains silent. The distance can be adjusted by modifying the program and keeping it within the range of the sensor.

Only one buzzer is used in this prototype, and it can produce only one type of sound. It gives rise to the challenge of deciding the direction of the object by a single sound. A delay is provided in buzzer sound to mimic the right direction of the object. For all the three directions, the buzzer sounds with different delay times. With different delay times, the user can understand the correct direction of the object and can act accordingly. Every human has 5 senses. Studies show that if any of the senses is lost, then remaining senses' working capability increases in comparison to the normal condition. This concept works here in recognizing the delay in the buzzer buzzing, and user comprehends directions easily with the buzzer sound delay. The smart cap is a closed loop control system. The closed loop control system of the smart cap is shown in figure 6. The aim or the output of the system is to guide the blind person for movement. Movement of person is compared with the output of the ultrasonic sensor using an Arduino UNO microcontroller board. The error signal is the difference between them. Arduino generates the control commands based on an error signal. These control commands feed into the plant, which is the cap here and decide to sound the buzzer or not. Based on the buzzer sound, the person again decides its movement. Movement of the person is feedback to compare with the ultrasonic sensor output, and it repeats the whole process. By this closed loop control mechanism, the cap becomes a smart cap. Arduino microcontroller sends the commands to sound or not sound the buzzer. These commands are written in Arduino IDE software which is based on C/C++ language. After compiling the commands, these are fed to Arduino UNO.

Figure 14. Simulation of Prototype

Simulation of Prototype

Proteus 8 has been used for the simulation of the prototype. The simulation circuit is shown in Figure 14. The following processes have been followed to simulate the prototype:

1. Firstly, the library of Arduino and ultrasonic sensors were installed.
2. From pick device window, Arduino, three ultrasonic sensors, and a buzzer were picked.
3. From the terminal window, seven GND and six Input were picked.
4. All the devices were connected, as shown in Fig. 14.
5. Using Arduino IDE, the code was verified, and the hex file was generated from the code.
6. By selecting the Arduino board in Proteus, the hex file was uploaded.
7. At last, the simulation was run. Based on simulation output and practical conducted in the real scenario, the resistance was adjusted for distance requirements and to set the buzzer.

Software Parts

The Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE) is a cross-platform application (for Windows, macOS, Linux) that is written in functions from C and C++. It is used to write and upload programs to Arduino compatible boards, but with the help of third-party cores, other vendor development boards.

Figure 15. Icon Arduino IDE

Practical Implementation

Overview: In order to implement the system, the programs are written using Java programming language for the main program implementation and C++ for microcontroller framework programming.

Software Parts: **Microcontroller Framework**

The Arduino provides the Arduino (Kumar, et al., 2011) Integrated Development Environment (IDE), which is a cross-platform application

written in the C++ programming language. It originated from the IDE for the languages Processing and Wiring. It is designed to introduce programming to artists and other newcomers unfamiliar with software development. It includes a code editor with features such as syntax highlighting, brace matching, and automatic indentation, and provides simple one-click mechanism to compile and load programs to an Arduino board. A program written with the IDE for Arduino is called a (Bhambare, et al., 2014) "sketch

Figure 16. The Arduino IDE interface

Conclusions

To design, our project's basic purpose is to connect the circuit's ultrasonic sensors to the blind circuit of the circuit system. Our project is already finished. The built circuit works very well. These are the ways used to offer obstacles to a variety of interesting materials. A simple, inexpensive, configurable and easy-to-use electronic guidance system is proposed to provide blind and visually impaired people with constructive helpers and support. The system has been designed, implemented, tested and verified.

Future Scope

1. Cumulative the range of the ultrasonic sensor and applying a technology for determining the speed of imminent obstacles.
2. Organization with various navigation software applications available on the internet so that new un-programmed purposes can be selected.
3. If the upcoming plan is a hole in the ground, it can be easily unspoken.
4. Provision for voice control using speech recognition.

5. Delivery for voice switch using speech credit.
6. Abridged size.
7. Abridged Weight.

References

Agrawal, M. P., & Gupta, A. R. (2018). Smart stick for the blind and visually impaired people. In *2018 IEEE 2nd International Conference on Inventive Communication and Computational Technologies (ICICCT)* (pp. 1-4). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICICCT.2018.8473206>

Bhambare, R. R., Koul, A., Bilal, M., & Pandey, S. (2014). Smart vision system for blind. *International Journal of Engineering And Computer Science*, 3(5), 5790-5795. ISSN: 2319-7242.

Castillo Guerrero, J., Quezada-V, C., & Chacón-Troya, D. (2018). Design and implementation of an intelligent cane, with proximity sensors, GPS localization and GSM feedback. In *2018 IEEE Canadian Conference on Electrical & Computer Engineering (CCECE)* (pp. 1-4). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CCECE.2018.8447697>

Chen, Q., Khan, M., Tsangouri, C., & Yang, C. (2017, July 31-August 4). CCNY smart cane. In *2017 IEEE 7th Annual International Conference on Cyber Technology in Automation, Control and Intelligent Systems* (pp. 1-4). Hawaii, USA: IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CYBER.2017.84466638>

Dastider, A., Basak, B., Safayatullah, M., Shahnaz, C., & Fattah, S. A. (2017, December 21-23). Cost efficient autonomous navigation system (E-Cane) for visually impaired human beings. In *2017 IEEE Region 10 Humanitarian Technology Conference (R10-HTC)* (pp. 1-4). Dhaka, Bangladesh: IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/R10-HTC.2017.8288910>

Hapsari, G. I., Mutiara, G. A., & Kusumah, D. T. (2017). Smart cane location guide for blind using GPS. In *2017 IEEE Fifth International*

Conference on Information and Communication Technology (ICoICT) (pp. 1-4). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICoICT.2017.8074651>

Kallara, S. B., Raj, M., Raju, R., Mathew, N. J., V R, P., & D S, D. (2017). Indriya - A smart guidance system for the visually impaired. In *2017 IEEE International Conference on Inventive Computing and Informatics (ICICI)* (pp. 125-129). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICICI.2017.8365244>

Kumar, A., Patra, R., Manjunatha, M., Mukhopadhyay, J., & Majumdar, A. K. (2011). An electronic travel aid for navigation of visually impaired persons. In *2011 Third International Conference on Communication Systems and Networks (COMSNETS)* (pp. 1-5). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/COMSNETS.2011.5716482>

Mutiara, G. A., Hapsari, G. I., & Rijalul, R. (2016). Smart guide extension for blind cane. In *2016 Fourth International Conference on Information and Communication Technologies (ICoICT)* (pp. 1-4). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICoICT.2016.7571917>

Nada, A. A., Fakhr, M. A., & Seddik, A. F. (2015, July 28-30). Assistive infrared sensor based smart stick for blind people. *2015 Science and Information Conference* (pp. 1-4). London, UK: IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SAI.2015.7237178>

Saaid, M. F., Mohammad, A. M., & Megat Ali, M. S. A. (2016, October 22). Smart cane with range notification for blind people. In *2016 IEEE International Conference on Automatic Control and Intelligent Systems (I2CACIS)* (pp. 1-4). Shah Alam, Malaysia: IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/I2CACIS.2016.7885287>

Sharma, T., Nalwa, T., Choudhury, T., Satapathy, S. C., & Kumar, P. (2017). Smart cane: Better walking experience for blind people. In *2017 IEEE International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Networks (CINE)* (pp. 1-4). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CINE.2017.8056245>

Su, B., & Wang, L. (2010). Application of Proteus virtual system modeling (VSM) in teaching of microcontroller. In *2010 International Conference on E-Health Networking, Digital*

Ecosystems and Technologies (EDT) (Vol. 2, pp. 375-378). IEEE.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/EDT.2010.5496468>